

Some UBF Church Activities of Brian Paul Kaess by Brian Paul Kaess

From about 1990-98, Brian Paul Kaess attended church & church activities at University Bible Fellowship (UBF) in Chicago and Pusan, South Korea. His Bible teacher Theresa Sohn first met him in the halls of Northeastern Illinois University, and invited him to UBF's Bible House near campus. Her and her husband, Dr. Augustine Sohn, Sr., have six children: Augustine, Francis, Agnes, Albert, Abraham & Sarah. Two of them are now medical doctors and Agnes received her Ph.D. from Chicago; Dr. Sohn said he admired Albert Schweitzer, the famous Missionary to Africa. Brian was invited many times to the UBF main church building on 6558 N. Artesian Ave. in Rogers Park, for one-to-one Bible study. UBF is a non-denominational Protestant sect. Brian began studying the Bible and, now and then, also attended Friday evening Prayer Meetings, where many new Christians would confess their sins. I asked myself, 'What happens if you don't?' Pauline, a secretary at NEIU told students not to go near UBF because they were bad news, some 'sort of cult.' They could also refer to 'newbies' as Sheep, which was a bit unsettling. In any case, I didn't Pauline too much heed. So thereafter, I became friends with the Sohn family, and they invited me to a couple of Spring Bible Conferences in a rented, recreation area in southern Wisconsin. They talked about 'house churches' and personal Bible study. We played volleyball and learned more about the Word of God and each other. World Mission! They would say things like: 'America was once a God-fearing, priestly nation.' They wanted to go back to the good old days of 19th century American Protestantism. They had an excellent church orchestra, and many of their hymns were Christian classics, such as, 'We Three kings of Orient are...' and 'All Hail the Power of Jesus' Name...' where they would sing: 'Ye chosen seed of Israel's race, Ye ransomed from the fall, Hail Him who saves you by His grace, And crown Him Lord of all.'

At one of these conferences, a large group of us (maybe 10-12 people) were in a large row boat rowing in the dark on a lake near the recreation site. Suddenly, because we were all rowing strongly, the boat tilted sideways and we almost tipped into the water. It caused the lot of us to laugh, just to relieve the tension. We were lucky, by the grace of God, that we had made it. In any case, the Lord was with us!

Some of the folks I met at UBF Chicago included 'big leaguers' such as Dr. Samuel Lee, Ron Ward, Sarah Barry, & Dr. James Rabchuk, as well as Matthew Bai (from Papa New Guinea), Yvonne, and Isaac. Dr. Samuel Lee, an Oxford man, had founded UBF in South Korea and had oversaw its growth abroad. Matthew had a South Korean wife and we chatted amicably. I was uncomfortable when Dr. Samuel Lee supported Serbia during the Bosnian conflict, because it seemed to contradict US Foreign Policy. He felt we should be supporting Serbia as 'a fellow Christian nation.' Also, Dr. Lee had me memorize the Ten Commandments and 'Divine Beatitudes' as part of my Lay Missionary training. No problem there.

Dr. Sohn would teach that the New Testament superceded the Old Testament, when Jesus said: 'I give you a new command: Love one another!' (John 13:34-35). He would also mention the verse: 'Whosoever believeth in Him, shall not perish, but have eternal life.' (John 3:15-16). He is now their North American Coordinator as of 2025. Then there was: "'Love the Lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your mind.' This is the first and greatest commandment." (Matthew 22:36-40). He also touched upon the historian Toynbee's views of 'challenge-and response.' His wife

Theresa gave me a copy of *Pilgrim's Progress* (1678) once.

Another time, in 1995, Dr. Augustine Sohn invited me to the Michigan State UBF Summer Bible Conference in East Lansing, which was attended by attendees from all over the globe. We stayed in a dorm room for a day or two during the conference and shared our faith through prayers. I also met Jenni, a UBF member and Michigan State grad, who gave me a walking tour of the campus and it turned out to be a pleasant day. Jenni also told me she was married with three kids. Later, with Dr. Sohn, I expressed my interest to join the U.S. military again, just because my clerk job looked like a bit of a 'dead end.' The Conference ended on a positive note and we returned to Chicago.

In Pusan, South Korea, I acted as a part-time missionary and gave an English Bible Message on Sundays to a group of Pusan UBF missionaries at their church near campus. This took a little bit of preparation. My 'Sheperds' were Kim Daniel and Mary, both South Koreans. They were supportive. Also, later, I taught a 'private' class of Bible English to a group of female UBF missionaries for a small fee. I did this at their invitation. This was going well, when I had a family emergency and had to return to the states.

Then there was the time I came home from the U.S. Marines in 1998 and, not long thereafter, Theresa Sohn invited me to their Christmas celebration at Northwestern University, which I attended. Lots of 'baby in the manger' & 'magi' stuff. That may have been the last time I really hung out with UBF.

My brother Garret had his own experience with Chicago UBF when he was studying at Truman College in his late teens. He began studying the Bible with them and became more Christianized. He would tell me on the phone: 'Jesus loves you...' I thought he had become a 'Moonie!' They took him on a 'retreat' to St. Catherines, Ontario, Canada sometime in the late 1980's, and he told me something funny happened while on the way there. He said he was riding with a number of male UBF missionaries in a vehicle, when a speeding station wagon was gradually cruising by.

Not sure what the station wagon wanted, they started waving and speaking Korean. But then, someone, in the rear of the station wagon, dropped his pants and 'mooned' the UBF vehicle, causing hilarious laughter to Garret right then and there. Then the station wagon sped up and drove off.

They eventually made it to the retreat, after visiting Niagara Falls, and settled down for some serious Bible study. To serious perhaps for Garret, who was having trouble balancing Bible study and school. He decided to focus on school first, and 'bailed' on UBF. I can't say I was much different in my early 30's when I needed more free time for socializing and working two jobs. UBF was ok though in opening my eyes more to the Christian world where not everything is based on self-interest and conflict, so it did serve a spiritual purpose. Praise the Lord! And remember... Jesus Saves!

